

Supplementary Data - S1

Predicted miRs targeting SLC43A2 mRNA

Noirmont M, Kukier P. 2025. Epigenetically complementary cancer interference.

Source of mRNA: miRNA target on entire gene of SLC43A2, transcript variant 1, mRNA.
NCBI Reference Sequence: NM_001284498.2

All miRNA targets predicted on SLC43A2 mRNA (full gene) by Pita, targetScan and miRanda, integrated in lncRNASNP2 database (<https://guolab.wchscu.cn/lncRNASNP#!/predict>)

miRNA ID	Score	Energy (kcal/mol)
hsa-miR-4638-3p	143.00	-41.98
hsa-miR-6089	141.00	-41.71
hsa-miR-339-5p	144.00	-37.84
hsa-miR-6849-3p	163.00	-37.34
hsa-miR-7114-3p	173.00	-36.80
hsa-miR-760	142.00	-36.78
hsa-miR-1343-5p	146.00	-36.28
hsa-miR-6862-3p	145.00	-36.27
hsa-miR-4734	142.00	-35.43
hsa-miR-6500-5p	149.00	-35.20
hsa-miR-6848-5p	146.00	-35.19
hsa-miR-2861	140.00	-35.04
hsa-miR-6821-5p	158.00	-34.96
hsa-miR-4632-5p	143.00	-34.68
hsa-miR-6803-5p	141.00	-34.61
hsa-miR-6846-5p	146.00	-34.55
hsa-miR-4512	147.00	-34.40
hsa-miR-6724-5p	144.00	-34.37
hsa-miR-1972	148.00	-34.24
hsa-miR-1207-5p	147.00	-34.22
hsa-miR-939-3p	143.00	-33.71
hsa-miR-6735-3p	142.00	-33.59
hsa-miR-4751	174.00	-33.39

hsa-miR-663a	149.00	-33.35
hsa-miR-6782-5p	145.00	-33.30
hsa-miR-1227-5p	145.00	-33.16
hsa-miR-6815-5p	147.00	-33.07
hsa-miR-4725-5p	160.00	-32.75
hsa-miR-2277-5p	167.00	-32.60
hsa-miR-874-5p	141.00	-32.58
hsa-miR-328-5p	140.00	-32.51
hsa-miR-1914-5p	140.00	-32.30
hsa-miR-6845-3p	142.00	-32.29
hsa-miR-6727-5p	141.00	-32.22
hsa-miR-4655-3p	142.00	-32.10
hsa-miR-615-5p	151.00	-31.96
hsa-miR-6812-5p	146.00	-31.92
hsa-miR-3147	140.00	-31.86
hsa-miR-1247-3p	143.00	-31.69
hsa-miR-4665-5p	141.00	-31.67
hsa-miR-3940-3p	166.00	-31.65
hsa-miR-4763-3p	140.00	-31.59
hsa-miR-3177-3p	152.00	-31.58
hsa-miR-4539	148.00	-31.52
hsa-miR-6741-5p	141.00	-31.49
hsa-miR-5088-5p	145.00	-31.47
hsa-miR-4466	159.00	-31.46
hsa-miR-6798-5p	149.00	-31.39
hsa-miR-3158-3p	150.00	-31.38
hsa-miR-8073	161.00	-31.27
hsa-miR-6086	141.00	-31.20
hsa-miR-6838-3p	142.00	-31.20
hsa-miR-4750-3p	141.00	-31.12
hsa-miR-6787-5p	146.00	-31.10
hsa-miR-7108-3p	145.00	-31.10
hsa-miR-6874-5p	141.00	-31.08
hsa-miR-6751-5p	141.00	-31.02

hsa-miR-514a-5p	141.00	-31.01
hsa-miR-4739	141.00	-30.94
hsa-miR-1910-5p	153.00	-30.90
hsa-miR-6875-5p	148.00	-30.88
hsa-miR-4723-3p	147.00	-30.84
hsa-miR-6792-3p	143.00	-30.84
hsa-miR-6756-5p	145.00	-30.78
hsa-miR-4690-3p	141.00	-30.71
hsa-miR-1470	146.00	-30.69
hsa-miR-8075	151.00	-30.68
hsa-miR-4459	140.00	-30.66
hsa-miR-4707-5p	144.00	-30.60
hsa-miR-6889-5p	143.00	-30.50
hsa-miR-4479	149.00	-30.49
hsa-miR-4532	147.00	-30.47
hsa-miR-6770-5p	172.00	-30.44
hsa-miR-4651	144.00	-30.41
hsa-miR-6744-3p	141.00	-30.41
hsa-miR-6749-3p	143.00	-30.41
hsa-miR-4745-3p	143.00	-30.36
hsa-miR-7108-5p	140.00	-30.36
hsa-miR-7106-5p	142.00	-30.35
hsa-miR-3936	153.00	-30.27
hsa-miR-662	144.00	-30.19
hsa-miR-6794-5p	145.00	-30.18
hsa-miR-615-3p	160.00	-30.16
hsa-miR-7851-3p	159.00	-30.05
hsa-miR-612	142.00	-29.96
hsa-miR-3180-3p	140.00	-29.95
hsa-miR-6851-5p	140.00	-29.87
hsa-miR-3944-3p	140.00	-29.82
hsa-miR-937-3p	144.00	-29.81
hsa-miR-7150	141.00	-29.80
hsa-miR-663b	146.00	-29.79

hsa-miR-6765-3p	150.00	-29.74
hsa-miR-1268a	140.00	-29.74
hsa-miR-1268b	140.00	-29.74
hsa-miR-4687-3p	148.00	-29.69
hsa-miR-3187-5p	140.00	-29.67
hsa-miR-1199-3p	150.00	-29.64
hsa-miR-4329	142.00	-29.60
hsa-miR-6775-5p	140.00	-29.53
hsa-miR-1182	153.00	-29.47
hsa-miR-4700-3p	146.00	-29.45
hsa-miR-6836-3p	142.00	-29.42
hsa-miR-584-3p	146.00	-29.42
hsa-miR-4508	143.00	-29.39
hsa-miR-6762-3p	141.00	-29.39
hsa-miR-6805-5p	143.00	-29.30
hsa-miR-873-3p	141.00	-29.28
hsa-miR-6784-3p	147.00	-29.27
hsa-miR-3150a-3p	142.00	-29.18
hsa-miR-5001-3p	147.00	-29.17
hsa-miR-7974	143.00	-29.13
hsa-miR-5008-5p	141.00	-29.12
hsa-miR-4642	142.00	-29.08
hsa-miR-7110-5p	140.00	-29.06
hsa-miR-330-5p	148.00	-29.05
hsa-miR-324-3p	144.00	-29.04
hsa-miR-3663-3p	141.00	-29.04
hsa-miR-1228-5p	148.00	-29.03
hsa-miR-4691-5p	140.00	-29.01
hsa-miR-6752-5p	145.00	-29.00
hsa-miR-6791-5p	140.00	-28.98
hsa-miR-4449	143.00	-28.98
hsa-miR-4513	158.00	-28.73
hsa-miR-6090	152.00	-28.73
hsa-miR-1266-5p	176.00	-28.71

hsa-miR-5587-3p	140.00	-28.71
hsa-miR-764	168.00	-28.70
hsa-miR-4254	148.00	-28.65
hsa-miR-1292-3p	151.00	-28.62
hsa-miR-6789-3p	147.00	-28.60
hsa-miR-1180-5p	151.00	-28.59
hsa-miR-4726-3p	140.00	-28.54
hsa-miR-7152-5p	144.00	-28.46
hsa-miR-1913	145.00	-28.36
hsa-miR-6785-5p	143.00	-28.32
hsa-miR-4540	167.00	-28.32
hsa-miR-6765-5p	141.00	-28.31
hsa-miR-6816-5p	142.00	-28.24
hsa-miR-4740-3p	152.00	-28.13
hsa-miR-4787-5p	144.00	-28.00
hsa-miR-4685-5p	141.00	-27.93
hsa-miR-3622a-5p	148.00	-27.91
hsa-miR-4767	142.00	-27.91
hsa-miR-6877-3p	149.00	-27.84
hsa-miR-7855-5p	143.00	-27.84
hsa-miR-6735-5p	140.00	-27.83
hsa-miR-3689d	149.00	-27.79
hsa-miR-6127	140.00	-27.68
hsa-miR-4450	147.00	-27.67
hsa-miR-6786-5p	140.00	-27.66
hsa-miR-6762-5p	140.00	-27.66
hsa-miR-4324	149.00	-27.62
hsa-miR-345-5p	147.00	-27.55
hsa-miR-8485	149.00	-27.52
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hsa-miR-661	142.00	-27.46
hsa-miR-637	155.00	-27.37
hsa-miR-128-2-5p	149.00	-27.34
hsa-miR-3943	145.00	-27.33

hsa-miR-6769b-5p	144.00	-27.31
hsa-miR-6753-5p	145.00	-27.31
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hsa-miR-2467-3p	151.00	-27.28
hsa-miR-769-5p	146.00	-27.28
hsa-miR-6784-5p	141.00	-27.25
hsa-miR-6763-5p	141.00	-27.24
hsa-miR-149-3p	140.00	-27.22
hsa-miR-762	141.00	-27.18
hsa-miR-4707-3p	142.00	-27.12
hsa-miR-6732-3p	144.00	-27.12
hsa-miR-4673	140.00	-27.11
hsa-miR-1234-3p	154.00	-27.10
hsa-miR-7113-5p	151.00	-27.06
hsa-miR-423-5p	140.00	-27.03
hsa-miR-596	146.00	-27.02
hsa-miR-4722-5p	140.00	-26.96
hsa-miR-6868-3p	148.00	-26.96
hsa-miR-6732-5p	149.00	-26.91
hsa-miR-6729-5p	142.00	-26.84
hsa-miR-3131	150.00	-26.84
hsa-miR-346	148.00	-26.80
hsa-miR-6802-3p	141.00	-26.79
hsa-miR-4253	154.00	-26.78
hsa-miR-503-5p	155.00	-26.73
hsa-miR-6717-5p	155.00	-26.69
hsa-miR-4285	140.00	-26.68
hsa-miR-6081	140.00	-26.66
hsa-miR-4269	150.00	-26.62
hsa-miR-4640-5p	145.00	-26.59
hsa-miR-619-3p	140.00	-26.57
hsa-miR-3934-3p	142.00	-26.53
hsa-miR-6863	144.00	-26.53
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hsa-miR-149-5p	141.00	-26.48
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hsa-miR-8055	158.00	-26.37
hsa-miR-6889-3p	160.00	-26.36
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hsa-miR-6511b-5p	141.00	-26.32
hsa-miR-6821-3p	140.00	-26.28
hsa-miR-6825-5p	141.00	-26.27
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hsa-miR-151a-5p	140.00	-26.26
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hsa-miR-671-5p	146.00	-26.14
hsa-miR-4688	146.00	-26.11
hsa-miR-6511a-5p	143.00	-26.11
hsa-miR-204-3p	146.00	-26.06
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hsa-miR-34a-3p	162.00	-25.99
hsa-miR-6720-5p	141.00	-25.94
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hsa-miR-6836-5p	142.00	-25.92
hsa-miR-5090	140.00	-25.90
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hsa-miR-6716-5p	151.00	-25.86
hsa-miR-34b-5p	142.00	-25.84
hsa-miR-4690-5p	157.00	-25.83
hsa-miR-6831-5p	150.00	-25.81
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hsa-miR-6877-5p	144.00	-25.79

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hsa-miR-1288-3p	155.00	-25.23
hsa-miR-675-5p	140.00	-25.22
hsa-miR-28-5p	154.00	-25.19
hsa-miR-3675-5p	143.00	-25.19
hsa-miR-4732-3p	155.00	-25.19
hsa-miR-4663	140.00	-25.17
hsa-miR-486-3p	141.00	-25.10
hsa-miR-6851-3p	141.00	-25.07
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hsa-miR-6829-3p	143.00	-24.98
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hsa-miR-2277-3p	141.00	-24.79
hsa-miR-138-5p	142.00	-24.79
hsa-miR-3193	152.00	-24.78
hsa-miR-6893-3p	156.00	-24.78
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hsa-miR-6796-5p	143.00	-24.72
hsa-miR-4692	143.00	-24.72
hsa-miR-8079	157.00	-24.64
hsa-miR-1225-3p	147.00	-24.63
hsa-miR-6856-5p	145.00	-24.62
hsa-miR-2278	151.00	-24.59
hsa-miR-3189-5p	141.00	-24.59
hsa-miR-4510	142.00	-24.56
hsa-miR-330-3p	148.00	-24.55
hsa-miR-939-5p	144.00	-24.53
hsa-miR-182-5p	169.00	-24.53
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Job ID:

https://guolab.wchscu.cn/lncRNASNP#!/predict_result?

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